

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE SYSTEM OF ENGINEER VEHICLES AND EQUIPMENT MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR AND THE FORMATION OF THE SPARE PARTS NOMENCLATURE

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Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of engineer vehicles and equipment (EVE) in the process of its operation. The article analyzes the factors that affect the efficiency of EVE maintenance and repair system functioning and formation of the spare parts (SP) nomenclature.

Keywords: engineer vehicles and equipment; technical condition; maintenance; combat operations; combat mission; spare parts.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Quality and timely maintenance and repair of EVE is one of the measures that supports the system of maintenance and repair in operational readiness for executing combat missions (CM). There is a contradiction, on the one hand between high requirements for the level of EVE TC during the execution of the CM, on the other hand, limited capabilities of the forces and means of repair units to maintain the given level of EVE TC.

Formulation of the problem. Analysis of the application of EVE in the area of JFO indicates an insufficient level of providing repair units with the necessary SP for maintenance and repair of EVE while execution of the CM.

Analysis of recent research and publications. When searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one cannot ignore the scientific works of V. Birkov [1], B. Demyanchuk [2], V. Sivak [3] and other researchers, who have quite deeply revealed most of the issues on this range of problems.

The purpose of the article. Conducting of the analysis of factors that affect the efficiency of EVE

maintenance and repair system functioning and formation of the spare parts (SP) nomenclature.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

Factors that affect the EVE TC during their intended use, accordingly affect the maintenance and repair system itself. Conventionally, they can be divided into external and internal [4].

External factors that affect the functioning of the EVE maintenance and repair system include: the peculiarities of EVE application in the performance of combat engineering tasks in modern conditions; the enemy's ability to damage EVE; physical, geographical and climatic conditions of the area of CM execution [4].

Modern conditions for the application of EVE require the introduction and use of vehicles created on the basis of tanks or on a special tracked base that is able to perform tasks under enemy fire, in conditions of mass fires, debris and destruction, on contaminated terrain, day and night, in a variety of climatic conditions.

It is also necessary to take into account the specificity of performing the tasks of engineering support of combat actions in modern conditions. This specificity is determined by: first, the heterogeneity of engineering support tasks, which leads to great dispersion along the

front and into the depth of operational formation of engineer units; secondly, a large variety of equipment in engineer units. At the same time, most EVE exist in small quantities, which not only complicates the system of EVE maintenance and repair, but also in case of failure of individual vehicles jeopardizes the execution of the CM.

Analysis of the peculiarities of engineer troops employment while conducting of combat operations (CO) over the past decades has shown that the average daily failure of EVE due to technical reasons and as a result of the enemy fire influence is on average 9-12%.

Internal factors that affect the efficiency of the EVE maintenance and repair system include: reliability of EVE samples; qualification of personnel; technical condition of EVE.

Reliability is understood as the ability of EVE to perform specified functions, while maintaining in time the values of the established operational indicators within the specified limits, which correspond to the specified modes and conditions of employment, maintenance, repair, storage and transportation [4]. The value of reliability actually consists in maintaining the tactical and technical indicators of the vehicle during operation.

The next internal factor that affects the efficiency of the EVE maintenance and repair system functioning is the qualification of personnel. EVE failure as a result of low personnel training, which leads to violation of the operating rules, and as a result – to the occurrence of failures, is accidental, but occasionally occurs.

One of the main factors that affect the efficiency of the EVE maintenance and repair system functioning is the technical condition of vehicles. In its turn, it mainly depends on their operating time from the beginning of operation and the period of operation. Along with other factors, the TC of the vehicles and, in its turn, the effectiveness of EVE maintenance and repair system functioning, is significantly influenced by their operating time since the beginning of operation and the period of operation. With the increase in the operating time and the period of EVE operation under the influence of operational factors due to wear, ageing, development of corrosion processes, etc., irrevocable processes of deterioration of their TC occur in systems, assemblies and units, which causes the occurrence of failures in operation.

Besides, more than 45% of EVE in the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine are in long-term and short-term storage, 70% of which are stored in open areas, which leads to the deterioration of the TC of individual parts, assemblies and units of EVE.

Thus, all the above factors, to a greater or lesser extent, affect the necessity to develop organizational and technical measures in order to increase the efficiency of the EVE maintenance and repair system functioning. These measures can be assessed by the duration of maintenance and repair work, which is an estimated indicator of the EVE system functioning.

The effectiveness of the EVE maintenance and repair system functioning largely depends on the SP nomenclature. At the moment, the problem of availability of SP in repair units is one of the most important, since timely provision or availability of the necessary quantity and nomenclature of SP allows repair units to quickly

carry out maintenance and repair of EVE. In turn, this will ensure the effective use for their intended purpose both in peacetime and in the course of CO execution. Therefore, in order to solve the problem of providing repair units with SP, it is necessary to consistently set and solve a number of partial tasks being equally important: firstly, the determination of SP nomenclature; secondly, the quantitative assessment of stocks for each item of their nomenclature.

Thus, the solution of the above-mentioned tasks is possible only under the condition of taking into account the complex impact on the needs of repair units in SR as a set of the most significant, actually existing factors.

It should be noted that a number of scientific works are devoted to the problems of providing repair units with SP, including the analysis of the impact of various factors on the SP nomenclature.

The purpose of the study is to analyze the factors that affect the formation of the SP nomenclature. The whole set of factors that affect the formation of the SP nomenclature is divided into four groups: design, operational, technological and organizational.

Design factors include the level of reliability, complexity and unification of the design of both the individual SP and EVE in general. They are determined by the shapes and sizes of the parts, the rigidity of the structure, the accuracy of the mutual location of the surfaces and axes of the conjugated parts, the correct choice of fits that ensure reliable operation of the conjugations. The need for SP increases with a decrease in the reliability of EVE.

In addition, the cost of the SP significantly depends on the operating time of EVE. It follows that the costs of the SP when employing EVE for 15-25 years are several times higher than in the initial period of EVE operation. As the term of use increases, there is a several-fold expansion of the nomenclature of SP, which is used to maintain the efficiency of EVE.

The development of mechanical engineering is characterized by a significant improvement in the technical and economic indicators of EVE. Basically, this is achieved due to the constant complication of the structure and, accordingly, increase in the nomenclature of structural elements. Depending on the operating conditions, the speed and loading modes of parts, mechanisms and EVE units, as well as the period of their trouble-free operation, change. In addition, the intensity of operation indicators are interrelated with the operating conditions. Therefore, in a number of cases, their cumulative impact on SP expenditure can be considered.

Technological factors depend on the quality of materials used for the manufacture of SP, the application of appropriate heat treatment and assembly works (centering, alignment, quality of fastening). It should be noted that technological factors are interrelated with design ones and in some cases, obviously, should be considered in aggregate. The factors considered have different importance for engineer units. Therefore, the most significant ones should be investigated first and in detail, as time and other resources allocated for research are, as a rule, limited.

Thus, as a result of the analysis of the factors that affect the formation of the necessary nomenclature of SP, those of them that collectively have the greatest impact on the dynamics of the use of SP in the EVE operation are determined. These include: operating time, number, age structure of EVE and their lifetime [5].

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

The analysis of factors affecting the efficiency of the existing EVE maintenance and repair system functioning, as well as the determination of SP nomenclature, allows us to conclude that a number of issues related to improving the efficiency of EVE use have not been resolved.

The most significant shortcomings of the EVE maintenance and repair system include: imperfection of the existing methodology for forecasting the SP nomenclature, which does not fully take into account statistical information on the failure-free operation of components and mechanisms of EVE; the SP nomenclature is determined without sufficient scientific justification of the intensity of malfunctions that occur while the EVE is in operation.

All this leads to a decrease in the EVE readiness ratio, the value of which in some cases does not meet the specified requirements.

References

1. Birkov V.P. Ensuring the reliability of engineer mechanical equipment during operation. Moscow: Military Publishing House, 1985. – 280 p.
2. Demyanchuk B.O. Automotive support of sub-units and units in different conditions of environment and warfare. Part 1. Training manual / B.O. Demyanchuk - Odessa: VA Publishing House, 2014. – 262 p.
3. Sivak V.A. Fundamentals of car production and repair technology: Training manual / V.A. Sivak, O.V. Verbovenko. – Khmelnytsky: NA PVU, 2003. – 143 p.
4. Baranov A.M. Analysis of factors that affect the efficiency of maintenance and repair system functioning of engineer vehicles and equipment / A.M. Baranov, Yu.M. Baranov, V.M. Ivansky, V.M. Malyuk // Collection of scientific works of the National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine. Series: military and technical sciences. – 2019. – №3(81). – P. 281–290.
5. Baranov A.M. Evaluation of efficiency of the maintenance and repair of engineer vehicles and equipment improved system functioning / Baranov A.M., Baranov Yu.M. // Collection of scientific works of the National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine. Series: military and technical sciences. – 2018. – No.1(75). – P. 292–300.